

Preliminary experimental analysis of sloshing-induced pressure drop in a parametrically-excited horizontal cylindrical tank

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Abstract – Non-isothermal sloshing in a scaled horizontal cylindrical tank is investigated experimentally using a custom experimental setup and methodology. An initial thermal stratification between the liquid and vapour phases is imposed in a tank partially filled to 50% with water, forming a two-phase water–water vapour system. The tank is subject to vertical sinusoidal excitation at the frequency of the first asymmetric longitudinal sloshing mode. The imposed excitation induces strong phase mixing, leading to ullage pressure collapse, breakdown of the thermal stratification, and enhanced heat transfer. A range of excitation amplitudes is examined, spanning regimes from mild to violent vertical sloshing. The results show that both the ullage pressure decay rate and the thermal destratification rate increase significantly with excitation amplitude. Owing to the tank’s transparency, detailed visual characterisation of the evolving flow regimes is achieved, enabling direct correlation with the measured pressure and temperature data.

Keywords: Pressure Drop, Thermal Destratification, Sloshing, Horizontal Cylinder

1 Introduction

In recent years, liquid hydrogen (LH₂) has emerged as a promising alternative to fossil fuels for commercial aviation, driven by the global effort to reduce aircraft emissions [1]. Although widely used in rocket propulsion, LH₂ has not yet been adopted at scale for aircraft propulsion. Key aspects of LH₂ integration, including tank design, dimensions, system architecture, and aircraft placement, remain open questions, and no dedicated technical guidelines or design criteria currently exist for cryogenic fuel tanks in commercial aviation. One limiting factor is the insufficient understanding of the coupled dynamic and thermodynamic responses of prospective fuel tanks to aircraft-specific excitations such as gusts, turbulence, and taxi operations.

This trend has led to an increased interest in the study of liquid sloshing inside LH₂ or LH₂-substitute fuel tanks for aircraft. The present research is carried out within the framework of the EU-funded Horizon project “HASTA” (*Hydrogen Aircraft Sloshing Tank Advancement*)¹, which aims to investigate the storage of liquid hydrogen for use as onboard fuel in large civil aircraft which are subjected to the EASA regulations CS-25 [2]. In order to achieve this aim, the project follows an approach based on extensive experimental investigations on the sloshing characterisation of LH₂ and substitute liquids, coupled with the development of numerical models which are calibrated on the experimental data. As part of this effort, preliminary tests have considered non-isothermal sloshing inside vertical cylindrical tanks with HFE-7200 as replacement fluid [3], and in a 2D disc-shaped tank with water [5]. It was found that sloshing regimes, which include swirling motions inside vertically-oriented tanks, lead to a more significant pressure drop [3].

The present paper reports on experimental tests involving vertical harmonic excitation of a reduced-scale horizontal cylindrical sloshing tank under controlled thermodynamic conditions in the liquid and vapour phases. Deionised water was used as

¹<https://www.hasta-project.eu>

the working fluid for investigating the sloshing-induced pressure drop phenomenon [5], owing to its safety and ease of handling compared to cryogenic liquids [6]. Although a biphasic water–water vapour system cannot fully replicate the thermodynamic properties of LH₂ [4], it can reproduce thermal stratification levels comparable to those observed in LH₂ tanks [5]. Given the particular relevance of vertical excitation in large-aircraft certification [2], vertical harmonic excitations near the first longitudinal sloshing mode (1,0) were investigated at large amplitudes [7]. The thermodynamic and dynamic evolution of the sloshing system was monitored, and the parameters related to the sloshing pressure drop phenomenon were studied.

This paper is organised as follows. The experimental setup, testing and data processing methodology are presented in Section 2. The results concerning thermal destratification and pressure drop for multiple amplitudes of excitation are presented and discussed in Section 3. Conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

2 Methodology

2.1 Experimental setup

This work considers a biphasic water-water non-isothermal sloshing system. Based on previous isothermal test results [7], an experimental rig was developed as shown in Figure 1a, with a schematic representation in Figure 1b. The main components of the test rig consist of a test section, a pressurisation system, a data acquisition system, and a camera system, which will be detailed next.

(a) The experimental test rig

(b) Schematic of the experimental test rig

Figure 1: Experimental rig for non-isothermal sloshing tests: (a) non-isothermal experimental setup; (b) schematic of the test setup layout

The test section consists of a scaled horizontal cylindrical sloshing tank (1). The tank dimensions were obtained by scaling a reference LH₂ tank fitting a typical mid-range aircraft falling under CS-25 regulations [2] and imposing a geometrical scale of $\lambda = 1:25$. The current setup is part of a series of tests planned at three different scales, this current scale being the smallest under consideration. The tested tank has an interior diameter $\phi = 80$ mm, length $L = 120$ mm, and wall thickness $t = 20$ mm, and is manufactured out of cast acrylic (PMMA). The wall thickness and material were chosen to limit heat losses to the environment while providing optical access. The end caps of the cylindrical tank are flat in order to minimise geometric complexity [7]. To measure the internal thermodynamic parameters, the following tank instrumentation is used. A piezoresistive Kistler 4262A series pressure sensor (5) was mounted in the upper part of the tank. A bespoke thermocouple array (6) was used to monitor temperatures in the liquid and vapour phases. The array consists of eight Type-K thermocouples placed in an acrylic tube reinforced with carbon fibre and epoxy resin, with an external diameter of 7 mm. The thermocouple junctions protrude 4 mm out of the acrylic tube to minimise the influence of the boundary layer on the temperature readings. Details on the exact placement of the thermocouples, as well as a photograph of the array are shown in Figure 2. For a tank filling level of 50%, five thermocouples are located in the vapour phase ($T_1 - T_5$) and three in the liquid phase ($T_6 - T_8$).

Figure 2: Thermocouple positioning and corresponding distances from the tank internal top wall.

Vertical sloshing forces are measured using two 100 N S2M load cells (7), with an accuracy class of 0.02%, installed between the tank support and the shaker. The APS 400 long-stroke shaker (3) was used to impose vertical sinusoidal motion to the tank, controlled using a Crystal Instruments Spider-80X controller (13) with closed-loop feedback from a variable-capacitance accelerometer (8). In order to impose the initial thermodynamic state inside the tank, it was filled to 50% with cold water from an external reservoir (11). Saturated vapour conditions in the ullage, and thus the desired thermal stratification, were controlled by a dedicated pressurisation system comprising a steam generator (2), an external reservoir (4) for initial wall heating, and a pressurisation line (9). The vapour generator consists of a 15 L steel vessel wrapped with a 2 kW flexible silicone heater and glass-wool insulation, with pressure measurement at the outlet. Heated vapour was supplied to the sloshing tank through a heated pressurisation line to avoid condensation along the way. A solenoid valve was used to control the injection cross-section.

All signals were acquired on a common time base using an NI cDAQ-9174 chassis (14) and recorded using MATLAB® (15): acceleration, pressure, and force using a sampling rate of 2100 Hz (NI-9234 and NI-9237), and temperature with sampling rate 95 Hz (NI-9212). In parallel, the liquid motion inside the tank was recorded with a Photron WX100 high-speed camera (16) at 240 fps, and the external wall temperature was monitored with a calibrated FLIR A6701 infrared camera (17) at 1 fps.

Following the description of the experimental setup, the next subsection presents the testing procedure and the complete list of conducted tests.

2.2 Test matrix and experimental procedure

In this work, a test matrix was devised to study the ullage pressure drop and temperature destratification under multiple amplitudes of excitation, as shown in Table 1. Given the shaker range limitations, vertical harmonic excitation tests were planned with the following acceleration amplitudes: 0.3 g (N03), 0.8 g (N08), 1.4 g (N14), 1.9 g (N19), and 2.4 g (N24). The chosen acceleration amplitude range ensures that violent liquid sloshing regimes typically encountered in fuel sloshing tanks are achieved [11]. To ensure repeatability, all tests were replicated between 2 and 3 times, as also indicated in Table 1. Each test was conducted for more than 40 s, which, given the time scale of the system dynamics at the excitation frequency of 4.3 Hz, ensured that the pressure drop phenomenon is adequately characterised. The ullage initial and final pressures P_0 and P_f are indicated, before and after the excitation, as well as the vapour and liquid mean temperatures, \bar{T}_v and \bar{T}_l respectively. Additional tests were conducted concerning the ullage relaxation characterisation, labelled "R".

The following experimental procedure was adopted, split into three phases: steam generator conditioning, followed by sloshing-tank preparation and pressurisation, and finally sloshing.

Table 1: Non-isothermal experiments test parameters.

Test no.	Test label	Rep.	Scale	Fill level	Excitation	Δt_s [s]	P_0 [kPa]	P_f [kPa]	\bar{T}_{v0} [K]	\bar{T}_{vf} [K]	\bar{T}_{l0} [K]	\bar{T}_{lf} [K]
1	N03	1	1/25	50%	Sine vertical	50	47.3	5.4	353.4	305	281.3	299.8
2		2				50	47.6	7.0	352.8	306.2	280.8	300
3		3				50	46.9	6.4	352.9	309.1	282.0	300.7
4	N08	1				50	47.3	6.6	352.8	300.9	280.4	300.5
5		2				50	47.2	6.4	352.8	301	280.1	300.6
6	N14	1				41	48.1	6.6	353.4	301.3	281.1	301.1
7		2				41	47.5	6.6	353.1	302	282.0	301.8
8		3				41	47.7	5.8	353.5	301.2	281.6	301.1
9	N19	1				41	47.7	6.2	353.5	301.7	281.2	301.5
10		2				41	46.9	6.1	353.2	301.2	280.6	301
11		3				41	46.7	5.4	353.3	301.1	280.8	301
12	N24	1				41	48.6	7.1	353.4	301	281.7	301
13		2				41	48.7	7.5	353.5	301.8	282.0	301.8
14		3				41	48.2	7.0	353.6	301.4	281.1	301.4

* Supplementary relaxation tests were conducted, labelled "R"

During the first testing phase, the steam generator is prepared. A vacuum is drawn in the generator (2) using the vacuum pump (12). One litre of deionised water is introduced into the generator, and the pressure is reduced again to 1.7 kPa to minimise air content. The heater is then activated, and the pressure rises gradually to a quasi-steady value between 176 and 184 kPa. As the liquid warms up, dissolved air is exsolved into the ullage. Because air is non-condensable and would alter the sloshing-induced pressure drop, the air–steam mixture is vented so that most of the air is purged. After closing the manual valve, the pressure is allowed to rise again to the value of 184 kPa. Simultaneously, the pressurisation line (9) is heated. Once the steam generator is conditioned, preparation of the sloshing tank begins. A vacuum is pulled inside the empty tank, which is then filled with cold water at 279 ± 1 K. A vacuum is pulled again inside the tank with water, down to ~ 1.7 kPa in order to remove any residual air from the ullage and from the liquid.

(a) Experimental procedure. $t_{p,0}$ – start of pressurisation, $t_{p,f}$ – end of pressurisation and start of relaxation, $t_{e,0}$ – start of excitation, $t_{e,f}$ – end of excitation

(b) Temperature variation during relaxation tests R01 and R02 run to establish the initial condition at the start of excitation ($t_{e,0}$)

Figure 3: Experimental procedure and relaxation test run to define initial condition for excitation ($t_{e,0}$).

Following the pressurisation system and sloshing tank initial conditioning, the tank can be pressurised. The timing corresponding to different experimental phases is shown in Figure 3a. The timings are chosen based on initial ullage relaxation tests

without sloshing, with the corresponding tank internal temperatures shown in Figure 3b. The ullage pressurisation commences at time $t_{p,0}$ and is applied in two stages. First, vapour is routed through the sloshing tank to the external reservoir (4) for 60 s in order to preheat the tank walls and reduce the wall condensation during testing. Then, the valve to the external reservoir is closed and the tank is pressurised with heated vapours to 101 kPa. The end of the pressurisation is marked by $t_{p,f}$. During ullage pressurisation, the water vapour saturation curve must be followed (details will be discussed in relation to Figure 8). The temperature-pressure saturation relationship is assessed according to CoolProp [12]. If the ullage state is observed to deviate from the vapour saturation conditions, it indicates that residual air is present in the ullage, and the test is consequently redone.

At time $t_{p,f}$, the ullage relaxation phase begins. The ullage pressure decreases exponentially due to vapour condensation at the liquid interface and the walls. The ullage relaxation ends at time $t_{e,0}$, which was chosen based on dedicated relaxation tests R01 and R02, Figure 3b. The thermocouple array temperatures are shown in various shades of gray corresponding to the thermocouple locations (lighter in the liquid and darker in the vapour phase). When the thermocouple located in the cold liquid near the interface reaches 326 K, the liquid-phase temperature stabilises over approximately 40 s before the temperature begins to decrease. Since a larger vapour-liquid temperature gradient is expected to lead to a larger sloshing-induced pressure drop, the vapour-phase initial condition was chosen at the onset of stratification stabilisation, setting the vapour temperature at $t_{e,0}$ to approximately 353 K.

Time $t_{e,0}$ indicates the start of the tank harmonic vertical excitation. The mean temperature profile of each test case at $t_{e,0}$ is shown in Figure 4a. Mean values are shown among repetitions, with gray bands representing the minimum and maximum values around the average. A maximum deviation of approximately 2 K is measured in both the vapour and liquid phases across all test cases. Figure 4b reports the temperature measured in the liquid near the interface, together with the mean temperatures of the thermocouples in the liquid and vapour phases. These temperature distributions indicate excellent repeatability of the initial thermal conditions at the onset of excitation, as well as uniform temperatures in the saturated ullage.

(a) Temperature distribution throughout the tank at $t_{e,0}$.

(b) Mean temperatures at $t_{e,0}$.

Figure 4: Pressure and temperature distributions at $t_{e,0}$, the beginning of the excitation.

3 Initial results

A series of initial experimental results is shown and discussed next. Time $t_{e,0}$ at the start of the excitation is taken as the reference $t = 0$ for these results. The ullage pressure evolution starting with $t_{e,0}$ is shown in Figure 5. The horizontal time axis was normalised to the excitation period of motion, $\hat{t} = t/T$. The mean pressure for each test case is shown, averaged over all repetitions, with the gray bands indicating the minimum and maximum values. The results show excellent repeatability for pressure decay and a strong dependence of the pressure decay rate on acceleration level. The corresponding pressures, mean vapour temperature \bar{T}_v , and mean liquid temperatures \bar{T}_l are listed in Table 1 for the start, $t_{e,0}$, and end, $t_{e,f}$, of the excitation. It is important to note the differences in pressure drop rate with increasing excitation amplitude. Larger excitation acceleration amplitudes lead to faster pressure drops. This result is significant, since a violent ullage collapse can pose problems related to pump cavitation [10].

Two cases, *N03* and *N24*, are selected for further comparison. A sample repetition for each case is shown in Figure 6, where pressure was normalised by its value at the onset of excitation, $\hat{P} = P/P_0$. The corresponding acceleration histories are shown on the right hand side axes, and liquid snapshots highlighting the influence of the excitation profile on the pressure evolution are also included. Three markers on the pressure curves indicate changes in logarithmic slope, assuming that the pressure decay can be modelled as a piecewise exponential function with different decay constants [9]: the first marks the end of relaxation and the onset of excitation-induced decay, the second the onset of significant liquid motion that breaks the initial stratification and enhances vapour–liquid mixing and condensation, and the third the approach to the final equilibrium state.

Figure 5: Ullage pressure decay for all tests. Mean values are shown, with error bands indicating minimum and maximum deviations around the mean.

For case *N03*, Figure 6a, the first longitudinal mode is excited. After 38 forcing periods of motion, the free surface starts impacting the upper wall, sharply increasing the pressure decay rate, and roughly 70 periods are required to reach quasi-equilibrium. In contrast, for the larger amplitude case *N24*, the first symmetric sloshing mode is excited and the sloshing-induced pressure drop is triggered in less than one period of motion, with only approximately 3 periods needed to reach equilibrium. This difference in system dynamics at different amplitudes is significant, indicating that sloshing regimes involving energetic vertical mixing lead to substantially increased rates of vapour condensation and corresponding ullage collapse.

Figure 6: Pressure decay and acceleration for the second test of *N03* and *N24*

For the same two cases, *N03* and *N24*, the corresponding temperature variations inside the tank are shown in Figure 7. The curves indicate mean vapour temperature \bar{T}_v , the liquid temperature near the interface T_6 , and the mean liquid temperature \bar{T}_l . Gray bands show variability among test repetitions. Ullage pressures are also shown on the right hand side axes, for reference. The temperature variations correspond to ullage pressure evolution, with drops in the ullage temperature and slower

increases in liquid temperature. In the case of the lower acceleration amplitude, *N03*, the temperature recorded by T_6 starts to oscillate after approximately 10 forcing periods with increasing amplitude, attributed to alternating exposure to hot vapour and cold liquid. In contrast, for case *N24*, thermocouple T_6 shows a larger initial temperature variation due to strong exposure to hot vapour, followed by a progressive decrease toward equilibrium. Equilibrium of the thermodynamic systems is reached much faster in the larger amplitude case, *N24*.

Figure 7: Tank temperatures and ullage pressures for tests *N03* and *N24*

The breakdown of the initial thermal stratification is indicated by the timing of the temperature evolutions. Temperature T_6 is the first to start oscillating as colder bulk liquid reaches the interface. As the sloshing amplitude grows, the ullage temperature decreases together with the pressure, reflecting enhanced vapour–liquid interaction and condensation which occurs faster at larger acceleration amplitudes. A later increase in liquid temperature is attributed to heat transfer from the upper warmed walls as well as mixing with the heated vapours.

Figure 8: P(T) curves for *N03* and *N24*

The evolution of the internal thermodynamic state can be further interpreted using the P-T diagrams in Figure 8. The ullage thermodynamic state is shown for all tests phases, during pressurisation ($t_{p,0} - t_{p,f}$) and during relaxation and sloshing ($t_{p,f} - t_{e,t}$). The saturation temperature T_{sat} was computed from the measured ullage pressure using CoolProp [12]. For both cases, the saturation and vapour temperatures agree well throughout the tests. Once the interfacial thermocouple intermittently contacts colder liquid during sloshing, deviations from the saturation curve appear, which are expected. For the higher-amplitude case *N24*, the deviation near the end of excitation is attributed to residual non-condensable gas, with air pockets likely released from the liquid during the violent sloshing.

4 Conclusions

An experimental setup and methodology for investigating non-isothermal sloshing in a scaled horizontal cylindrical tank were presented. The facility enables controlled studies of the thermodynamic evolution of a two-phase water–steam system under vertical accelerations up to 2.4 g, with transparent tank walls providing optical access to the free-surface dynamics. Experiments conducted at a 50% fill level, with saturated vapour injected into the ullage, established an initial temperature stratification of approximately $\Delta T \approx 73$ K between the liquid and vapour phases. Measurements of ullage pressure and temperature revealed a pressure drop driven by vapour condensation into the liquid phase. Increasing excitation amplitude resulted in progressively more violent sloshing, enhanced phase mixing and thermal destratification, and consequently stronger condensation and higher ullage pressure decay rates, with a maximum observed at 2.4 g for the present configuration.

The experimental approach provides a robust basis for quantitative analysis of coupled momentum–heat transfer and phase-change phenomena in non-isothermal sloshing flows, and for systematic investigation of scaling effects in horizontally oriented tanks.

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References

- [1] E.W. Stautner, K.S. Haran, P.J. Ansell and C. Minas, *Aircraft Cryogenics*, 1st ed.; Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 12-13.
- [2] European Union Aviation Safety Agency. Certification Specifications and Acceptable Means of Compliance for Large Aeroplanes(CS-25), Amendment 28, 15 December 2023.
- [3] P. A. Marques, A. Simonini, L. Peveroni and M. A. Mendez, "Experimental analysis of heat and mass transfer in non-isothermal sloshing using a model-based inverse method", *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 231, pp. 120871, 2023.
- [4] S. Ahizi, P. A. Marques, F. M. F. Monteiro, L. M. Gonzalez, F. Gambioli, H. Scheufler, R. Abarca, and M. A. Mendez, "Scaling laws for experimental characterization of sloshing effect in liquid hydrogen tanks", in *Proceedings of ISOPE*, Rhodes, Greece, 16-21 June 2024.
- [5] F. Saltari et al., "Experimental investigations on the sloshing-induced pressure drop in tanks for hydrogen-powered aircraft", in *AIAA SCITECH 2024 Forum*, Orlando, FL, USA, 8-12 January 2024.
- [6] M. E. Moran, N. B. McNelis, M. T. Kudlac, M. S. Haberbusch, and G. A. Satornino, "Experimental Results of Hydrogen Slosh in a 62 Cubic Foot (1750 Liter) Tank", in *Joint Propulsion Conference, Indianapolis*, IN, United States, 27-29 June 1994; No. E-8916.
- [7] F. Festila, L. Constantin, M. Casapu, A. Stefan, P.V. Rosu, "Experimental sloshing regimes in horizontal cylindrical tanks", in *EASN Conference*, Madrid, Spain, 14-17 October 2025.
- [8] C. Ludwig, M. E. Dreyer and E. J. Hopfinger, "Pressure variations in a cryogenic liquid storage tank subjected to periodic excitations", *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 66, pp. 223–234, 2013.
- [9] F. Gambioli, A. Malan, and F. Mastroddi, "On the relationship between pressure collapse rate and Nusselt number during sloshing in cryogenic liquid hydrogen tanks", *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 183, Oct. 2025.
- [10] A. van Foreest, M. Sippel, and A. Isselhorst, A fast engineering tool for simulation and design of propellant management systems in liquid propelled launcher stages, in *EUCASS 2009*, Versailles, France, 6-9 July 2009.
- [11] L. Constantin, J. De Courcy, B. Titurus, T.C.S. Rendall, J.E. Cooper, "Nonlinear damping effects in vertically vibrating systems with violently sloshing liquid", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Volume 544, 2023.
- [12] Bell, Ian H and Quoilin, Sylvain and Wronski, Jorrit and Lemort, Vincent, "Coolprop: An open-source reference-quality thermophysical property library", *ASME ORC 2nd International Seminar on ORC Power Systems*, 2013.